

A Framework to Achieve Quality and Excellence in Higher Education: A Literature Review

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ABSTRACT

Educating large numbers of people to a high standard and disseminating knowledge can be considered as the main objectives of today's higher education sector. An effective framework for delivery mechanism by enhancing the functional responsibility and its effective execution will help the nation in achieving quality and excellence in higher education. Present paper tries to explore framework for achieving quality and excellence in higher education by analysing the various functional aspect of higher educational system in the country. After extensive literature survey and analysing the research work of eminent researchers and thinkers, it is concluded that higher education has become larger and more central to society and individuals; hence, there a need to develop framework including different functional components for performance indicator and measurement. It is suggested that various enhancement function should be executed primarily in systems of high trust, whereas the accountability function has to be developed to prevent bad quality of institutions and programs, and thus to protect the beneficiaries i.e. students and society. Universities need to be consciously and explicitly managing the processes associated with the creation of their knowledge assets and to recognise the value of their intellectual capital to their continuing role in society and in a wider global marketplace for higher education.

Keywords-- Quality and Excellence, Higher Education, Intellectual Capital, Global Marketplace

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laboratory which tests the metal of philosophic truth and suggests how these truths can be achieved. People face circumstances throughout their life and acquire experience and outcome of these acquired experiences is education. This process through which experiences are acquired is a social process and are directly related and highly influenced by prevailing social factors. Thus, all education is for environment and it is a complete social process and its function is to preserve the social heritage and to enrich it and flourish it. Entire learning is an outcome of social interaction and social motivation. It is a process of directed learning, it enables people to develop their social standing, and facilitate them to become efficient, effective and useful member of the society. Education is a continuous process, it is an acquired knowledge and experience, it is a profound philosophical exploration of transmitting knowledge in human society; it is a development of overall human personality, it creates and transfer knowledge to successive generations, it is a harmonious integrated growth, it is effective for the welfare of the society, it introduces individuals to social and human values, ethics, morality, humanity, consciousness, prudence, wisdom, intelligence, commitment, virtue, honesty and character, it teaches human soul to love beauty, it is a liberal discipline and conservator of culture, it enable individual to appreciate life, it is an instrument of change and social reforms, it discipline the mind, it convert closed and empty mind with an open one, it is lighting of fire to curse darkness, it is a key to open the golden doors of freedom, it transform mirrors of mind into windows, its aim is the knowledge of values not of facts, it is a journey from darkness to light, it is unilateral as well as bi – polar in nature and its sociology focuses on social forces which help people in gaining experience.

I. INTRODUCTION

Education is not only schooling the children's or a kind of instruction which are imposed on juniors by the seniors. It is a lifelong process and tries to develop the innate potentialities of the individual. It harmoniously empowers the human being with social, spiritual, intellectual, physical and aesthetic strength. It is a development of collective personality through social process of educational institutions. All educational programmes become consistent and progressive whose strength comes from moral values of the society and their foundations are laid on true philosophy. Education is the

II. STATUS OF HIGHER EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTE: AN OVERVIEW

Higher Education sector has witnessed a tremendous increase in the number of Universities/University level Institutions & Colleges

since Independence. Higher education plays important role in integrating the society by creating and exploring new knowledge and transmitting it to students and fostering innovation. Quality teaching in higher education is essential and it influence students learning outcome to a great extent. But in respect to foster the quality teaching it is paramount important for higher educational institutions to ensure that the offered education is highly futuristic and is according to the expectations of students and meeting the present and future requirements of employees. Internationalization in higher education needs high degree of accountability and transparency. Generally institutional accountability, quality and improved performances of higher education institutions are insisted not expected. But from recent past trend shifted and started focusing on developing research in teacher education across the world. Teacher quality education, academic excellence and expertise are essential element to bring improvement in education. It is only possible if we produce highly qualified teachers. Teachers are soul of academic and educative process. They have thorough knowledge of relative subjects and have quest to know the people, society and have clear vision about everything which comes into contact. They have a desire to unearth hidden information's and reality of the universe and are burning soul to acquire diversified range of knowledge, their curiosity to learn never satisfy. They have definite outlook on life, optimistic or pessimistic or negative, materialistic or idealistic. Most of the countries realises the importance of teaching and initiated teacher education programmes to produce high quality teachers. Almost in all developed nations teacher education has shifted from training the teachers to transfer knowledge and enabling them to practice an instrumental role of producing knowledge. In modern education era it is considered that to become a teacher or being a teacher or doing teacher research not only promote reflection about personal performance in teaching, but also it stimulates a quality process of self-assessment in challenging academic circumstances to identify their academic status, strength and weakness. Thus, in order to make teacher a quality teacher and enabling them to practice the critical and challenging role they should be supported and equipped with overall skills that based on research-oriented education.

Developing and maintaining quality teaching is not easy, it highly depends upon teaching and academic programs, research activities and scholarship, academic equipment's and overall infra, students, staffing, facilities, services to the community, healthy academic environment, global academic equity and networking, exchange of academic knowledge, expertise and academic interaction, globally integrated research projects, culture, values and ethics. According to government data release, number of colleges and universities in India reached 39,050 and 903, respectively in 2017-18. Today Indian has 36.64 million students enrolled in higher education. Gross Enrolment Ratio in

higher education reached 25.8 per cent in 2017-18 from 25.3% in 2014-2015 and expected 30% GER by 2020-21. India has the world's largest population of about 500 million in the age bracket of 5-24 years and this provides a great opportunity for the education sector. The mission of higher education is to achieve access, equality, justice, quality, employability, inclusiveness and create a knowledge society economy. The country has become the second largest market for e-learning after the US. The sector is expected to reach US\$ 1.96 billion by 2021 with around 9.5 million users. According to one of the study report, the percentage of students enrolled for Masters (PG) courses had been 9.61% while a small proportion i.e. 0.79% of the total number of students has enrolled for research courses (Ph.D. / M.Phil.). Similarly, only 2.60% and 0.61% of the total number of students has been enrolled in Diploma/certificate courses. Hence the secondary information as provided by the UGC shows that conversion of students enrolled for graduation to post graduate courses is very low. The main aim of this paper is to explore the reasons of low conversion as well as helps to find out the motives of students pursuing higher studies. In order to bring improvement in higher education research-based education system is necessarily required. It is welcomed by researchers in higher education and got importance in public discussion. Through research base education teachers explore their teaching potential and develop the requisite knowledge, skills and expertise and transform themselves into academic leaders capable of implementing and executing national reform agenda.

III. AIMS OF EDUCATION AND ITS NEED

Education is one of the most important and purposeful activity. By educating we intend to craft students and try to bring effective and positive changes in them. It is holy act and is a conscious effort and it moves on definite aims and objectives. All academic activities like determination of curriculum and achievement of students are measured under the shadow of its aims and objectives. It is needed to bring certain desirable change in human being through education and to give direction to the academic activity. Without aim and objectives of education nothing can be achieved. It will be just like a boat without its rudder or a blind alley or gun without bullet. Aims and objectives give vision, mission and direction. Human life is full of aims and objectives, every stage of human growth and development had some predetermined aim, like spiritual aim, vocational aims, knowledge and information aim, character building aim, culture aim, moral aim, social aim, carrier growth and development aim, socio-economic integration and political aim, educational leadership aim, personality development aim. These predetermined aims and objectives of life determine aims of education and these aims and objectives of education change from age to age.

IV. NATURE OF EDUCATIONAL AIMS

It is herculean task to identify and set aims of education in present competitive educational environment. If we want to know the aims of education, then first and foremost we have to know the nature of aims. Aims of education change with passing time; they are relative, eternal and universal and are not fixed. To understand exactly what is the nature of aims of education we have to go through two distinct philosophies of life that is idealism and pragmatism. It is truth that philosophies of life are always reflected in the aim of education and have a deep impact on the society. Idealism philosophies teach us to develop and adopt absolute, ultimate, eternal and universal values which are highly spiritual in nature. It generally moves on the straight and simple path in which it pleads knowledge for knowledge sake. In the idealistic environment education is considered for general and ethical development of a society. It promotes education for complete living. It particularly considers that aims of education are fixed and cannot be changed; they are predetermined, absolute, universal, spiritual and highly idealistic in nature. The core aim of idealistic education is to realise predetermined, pre-existing, absolute and universal values.

Pragmatism philosophy is known as the realistic approach of life and it deals with life as it is not as it should be. In realism prevailing environment play important role and social, political and economic factors of life are taken into consideration. The prevailing socio-economic conditions of life determine the aims of pragmatic education. It is just contrast of idealism and does not believe in absolute and eternal values. Education must be futuristic and base on exploring potentialities of the individual. It must be enough to prepare future generation for the economic and social system of the nation. Thus, all higher education must be combination of both philosophies as they are two side of human coin. In fact, idealism is a root of human tree and pragmatism is its branches. Learning throughout life is the key in the globalized world of the 21st century and good education to cater the 21st century requirement is possible if we have absolutism, spirituality, idealism, universality and value with realism, economic, socio political factor.

V. OBJECTIVES AND RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Higher educational institutes in India is passing through a transformation stage. Several policy initiative and government intervention are initiated to meet the growing market demand for education and fulfil the stakeholder's aspirations. It is observed that most of the government policies focussed on building quantity in terms of student's enrolment and opening new institution

but very less effort is made toward bring quality and achieving excellence. The present research article is undertaken to

1. To study and understand the various factors affecting quality in higher educational institutions and develop a framework for achieving quality and excellence in higher education by analysing the various functional aspect of higher educational system in the country.

The present research paper is based on secondary data. The basic approach adapted in this paper is a balance of qualitative and quantitative methods. The analysis has been done in a contextual setting and focuses on the evaluation of strategies and theories collected from different literature of previous research work. The qualitative approach has been justified by giving numerical figures. Due to the difficulties in obtaining information from primary sources, the present paper is based on secondary data resources i.e. information that has already been collected and is available. The data is mainly extracted from government sources, university websites, books, journals, articles, research papers, blogs, etc. After extensive literature survey and analyzing the research work of eminent researchers and thinkers, it was systematically arranged, and appropriate analysis was carryout. Some of the conclusion based on the study are also drawn

VI. LITERATURE REVIEW

Education is a basic requirement and it is being accepted by all nations. To provide better education to the students all nations are working in integrated manner. Globally large number of educationist, philosophers and professionals carried out their research activities and gave their views. All the studies produced facts of the time period and gave direction for other to analyse it and to contribute in noble cause 'education'. It is found that educationists are most egoist people on earth, they present the same thoughts with different vocabulary and contradict other. But their contradiction becomes source of learning for next generation.

Hutchins (1992) argued that quality management involves more than monitoring and guidance. He considers that it is important to focus on understanding and developing the potential of workforces. He further stated that success will follow when an individual is motivated to do a job, and then they explore ability and develop confidence to take up the task, Kutz, Groden and Zamel (1992) found that skills models adopted by the schools and higher education institutions generally highlight students error rather than building on students existing competencies, McIntyre (1993) consider that when measure became a target, it is consider as a good measure, Harvey & Knight (1993) consider that models of quality as fitness are for purpose and value for money, Van Vught & Westerheijden (1994) found that quality in higher education is closely associated with economy and government want to achieve its ambition by bringing

changes in the institutions working conditions and styles and due to which institutions are working in competitive and economical way, Salter & Tapper (1994) consider that value for money is closely related to the economic ideology, that education should contribute to a nation overall growth and development, McMillan & Cheney (1996) found that customer model developed gap between the student and the educational process and it compartmentalises the educational experiences as a product, Clotfelter (1996) said that quality play instrumental role in higher education institutions survival; it largely depends upon teacher and students quality. If institutions want smooth survival with growth and development then it has to maintain quality by implementing quality policies and by adopting quality mechanism, Woodhouse (1996) consider that fitness for purpose has become ultimate approach to evaluate quality in higher education, Winston (1999) considers quality of education is most important for institution survival and it largely depends upon student and teachers, institution has to adopt some effective quality mechanism in choosing the students. According to him that selective competition will make higher educational institutions more hierarchical and exclusive, O'Brien & Hart (1999) found that concept of quality is generally used as competitive weapon which ultimately result in a profit and consumerism culture. They further found that institutions are demanded to enable students with transferable skills which have been accompanied by performance indicators, Brennan & Shah (2000) reveal that academics feels detached from the process of evaluation. According to them that process of evaluation largely focus on managerial control and institutional quality instead of individual academic's teaching and learning, According to David Blunkett, UK Secretary of State for Education (DFEE, 2000 p.3) that in this new economy, it is education and skills which shape the opportunities and rewards available to individuals, McGivney (2001) found that attracting and supporting non-traditional students remains important issue, Dill (2001) found that generally focus on institutional missions do not evaluate quality of the educational process and its outcomes but strengthens external influences on the performance of the institution, Golde & Drove (2001) argued that to what extent institutes are able to train the next generation of researchers, (Morley 2003) found that academicians consider quality as a power. He further stated that there is feeling among the academic fraternity that quality has been used as an integral component of the spread and location of government power, George (2007) found that students perceives themselves as customers purchasing a product, Eagle (2007) found that the concept of customer defined quality is problematic, Harris (2008) found that there is a deep concern among the academic participant that a neoliberal university are economic oriented rather than a culture imperative, which in result makes its internationalisation degenerate into instrumentalism, Chattopadhyay(2009) found that most of the private

institutes are compromising with quality in higher education, especially professional and technical education. They are considering cost cutting much more important than quality, Burns (2010) during his period of study found that countries are taking interest in promoting action research in the teacher education curriculum, Saunders (2011) found that conceptualization of students as a customer will impact negatively on student learning and lead to a passive approach to education, Karaim (2011) found that by reaching 2025, the projected demand for global higher education will reach 263 million students, Cheng (2014) found that sometimes academics wonder the criteria and standards which are used to measure purposes and really represent what is truly quality, Khola (2014) found that in past and as well as in present many studies reveals that learning can be highly influenced by the degree to student participation and their commitment to their learning, Dr S.M. Tariq Zafar, Dr Waleed Hmedat and Dr D.S. Chaubey, (2018) found that, for the development of the society and nation as a whole, it is essential to find the means of developing academic leadership, nurture it and support with all means for doing the right thing at the right time

VII. IMPLEMENTING QUALITY IN HIGHER EDUCATION

Quality in higher education is a transformation of stakeholders or it can also be termed as a fitness for purpose. It is an alignment of consistency of outcome with the institution's vision – mission and goals, demonstrated by learning and service outcomes at exceptional levels and by a shared culture of quality. To cater the growing demand of higher education there is need to produce thoughtful graduates who in due academic process have acquired ethical and social values to respect others as human beings with intrinsic rights, have culture and rootedness, have a passion and avocation to serve, have analytical and problem solving skills with competitiveness that aligned with national, global and industry required standards, have ability, willingness, passion to acquire competency and have thirst to learn continuously throughout the life.

It is widely accepted truth that most of the nation's higher education scenario does not match with these global required quality standards. Thus, there are justified reasons to make an assessment of the quality of the nation's educational institutions. Most of the academic institutions worldwide assumed that quality can be determined by their internal resources in which faculties with required qualification, experience, admissions broacher, library facilities, modern campus infra, assessable outputs, and optimal utilization of academic resources, highly trained and employable graduates. But in present global and highly competitive era this approach and justification of determining quality in higher education is not complete, it is only a value addition and does not measure the ability, efficiency and

competency which students have developed and acquired by going through the courses which institute has offered. Generally, all acquired competencies are broadly categories into understandable, recall and problem solving. Understanding is comprehension and requires explanations and vocabulary development. In this student demonstrate ideas that predict and evaluate cause and effects. Recall is a kind of competency in which student gain knowledge by reading, viewing, listening, assimilating and use to demonstrate when it is required. Student acquire competency of problem solving by developing expertise through solving text book types of problems which can be used in handling real life situations. Students have to understand these core concepts and they must know clearly as what kind of competency they required to face the practicality of life.

VIII. ADOPTING EXCELLENCY IN HIGHER EDUCATION

For smooth survival of educational institutions and for the betterment of socio-political, economic growth and development of the nation it is paramount important for the higher education institutions to develop and adopt excellence in their overall academic system. It is an expectation and everlasting goal. Excellent higher education institutions have to develop and facilitate the achievement of the mission and vision. They have to develop institutional values strategically and systems which are essential for sustainable success.

In general, the term excellence is used to refer very good or outstanding performance. In higher education it has multiple meaning depending upon context it is related and can be equated with the reputation and outstanding of institutions. It highly rely on the perception of student experience and varying missions of institutions according to time period. Higher education institutions have to identify it at the institution level, among faculty, in departments or individual members of staff. Institutions must apply it in diversified range of activities, roles and functions. It must be applied in all factors of the institutions, like management, academic service delivery, experience of staff and students and outputs from study and research.

Excellence is a social phenomenon and based on theoretical and cultural consideration. Its objective is highly focused on culture and values of higher education and drives the motivation from continuous improvement. To develop and maintain excellence, higher education institution has to assure quality and has to improve the quality of service it is providing to students and to teaching fraternity. It has to improve quality of teaching; it has to enhance thinking, attitudinal and behavioural capabilities of students in order to match the passé of changing world and enabling them to participate in crafting their individual and collective future. It has to improve the level of student achievement and the scale of resource provision.

Higher education institute has to raise their standards of performance in structural and organizational level logically and operationally to attain excellence. Institutions must develop competency-based learning standards that comply with existing global standards to achieve quality and has to develop effective integration of the intellectual discipline, ethos and values associated with liberal education. For efficient and effective quality assurance monitoring and evaluation, institutions have to design and adopt outcome-based approach. Higher educational institutions to establish excellence have to increase effectiveness of quality assurance system and quality, efficiency and effectiveness. They have to adopt education by accretion and have to store education as formation of mind. They have to adopt education for future preparation and direction, education for growth, development and for mental discipline. They have to adopt education as process to bring social change, progress and socialization.

IX. ESSENTIAL REQUIREMENT FOR IMPROVING QUALITY OF HIGHER EDUCATION

Developing Learning Society

With increasing information technology, education has grown many folds. This growing education has to be transformed by the higher educational institutions into learning society because in future all human activities require contributions from experts. Higher education institutions have to invest more not only into physical infra, but they have to give much more importance to teaching, learning and research programmes. They have to transform educated society into learning society in order to cater the unforeseen future.

Strategic Industry and Academia Integration

Higher educational institutions have to develop and maintain strategic relation with industry. Output of educational institution is input for industry. To match the requirement of industry institutes, have to adopt industry required teaching and learning. Educational institution job is not to produce only graduate with degrees but to produce graduate with skills which enable them to adopt prevailing conditions in competitive and hostile global environment. Institutions have to strategies industry participations through their active representations. Institutes have to develop curriculum with their consultation. Industry must be engaged and encouraged to induct students as a trainee in their projects. Teachers must be encouraged to use case studies and industrial reports in teaching. To develop quality and competitive strength institutions have to standardise the syllabi and align it with industry requirement. A well-designed syllabus is prepared strategically and mutually. It requires set of goals, objectives with systematic sequence of topic and study material which must be mutually accepted, acknowledged and formally approved by the institution

and industry. It must cover knowledge, learning attitudes, ability, and general cognitive ability which enables students to develop awareness. Institute must adopt action competence, key competences, and Meta competencies along with competence performance model, modified competence performance model to groom students according to industry requirement. Mutually developed syllabus must be industry oriented rather than testing and examination oriented. Survival of educational institutions depends upon student's success. Industry survives on skill full, efficient and effective human resources which they get from educational institutions. The institution objective will be attained if its inputs are groomed with quality and excellence and are transformed from raw to efficient and effective output through rigorous academic process and are getting absorbed with appreciation. Such output will establish institutional respect and goodwill in the society.

Increase Incentives to Motivate Teacher and Researchers

Higher education institutions are recognised by their quality teaching which is possible if they have research-oriented teachers and complementing salary and incentive policy. Teacher's research orientation makes institution more competitive. Research orientation develops respective teacher's academic strength which is translated into good teaching. Research orientation develop attitude of teachers to find solution to the related problems and this attitude is core strength of an excellent academic institution. For survival, growth and development industry and students expect innovative and carrier-oriented courses with required skills. Such specialised and innovatively designed courses make student competitive and employable. These new courses can be successful if institutions have motivated teachers and motivation comes only through compensation and effort recognition. To develop competitive strength institution must make effective research policy with attractive compensation on one side and on other side it must encourage its academic assets teachers to adopt research base teaching to groom student.

Innovative Approaches

In the era of competition survival is possible if the educational institutions are highly innovative to reframe, redesign and reinvent themselves. Being an innovative means that institution has more than acquiring the competitive technologies or implementing new approach. Innovation leads to structure programs and practices of the institution systematically. It promotes healthy and effective changes. It invents, reframe and reinvented academic approaches and the ongoing creative and productive advancement of student, teachers and of institution. It offers multiple opportunities for academic growth and development. It paves the way for improved learning and socio – cultural advances. Strategic innovating practices implement innovation cycle where new ideas are generated, implemented tested and knowledge is disseminated which enable academic participant. Technological advancement facilitates

innovation and creates new ideas to educators which can be shared and discussed with others. Thus, if institutions want to be a leader it has to become innovator.

Research Base Teachers Education and Training

In present highly innovative and competitive environment quality in higher education can be achieved only through sufficient training process. Institutions have to provide research base training to the teachers in order to make them more productive in teaching. Institutions have to develop research excellence framework with an aim to train teachers and to promote research base teaching. In higher education most, teachers are working without any training in teaching, learning and evaluation technique. Therefore, it is necessary to provide rigorous one-month training to the untrained teachers in order to develop confidence in them. Provided training must focus on developing pedagogical knowledge, in depth subject knowledge, content knowledge, effective skills and dynamic attitudes necessary for effective teaching, desire and passion to understand reasons of human growth and development, effective communication skills, strong sense of ethics and capacity for reinventing and ongoing learning. Institute must associate retire teachers and industry professionals who are renowned and have high reputation to share their teaching and research experience with untrained teachers and explore their academic potential and mentor them to excellence. Institute also train teachers as how they develop confidence among students, act as a counsellor, a guide and a friend. They must help students to think rightly and to do rightly, they must make student feel nobly, they must make student to develop universal love and brotherhood.

Strategic Governance and Management

Society and industries have a high degree of expectation from higher educational institutions to demonstrate strong commitment to excellence in institutional mission and vision. Institutional practices, planning, resourcing and setting ethos and style are highly related and influenced by the strategic directions. It is expected that executive management team and governing bodies will set the institutional goals to promote excellence. To develop excellence, institutions have to bring improvement and willingly they have to make periodical assessment of their weakness and strength. They have to demonstrate high degree of determination in setting standard and for its achievements.

Setting high Standards of Academic Achievement

Institutes have to set their standard high if they want to become leader in respective field. Academic performance of students and academic achievement of the teachers demonstrate the status of the institute and it is consider as a key measure of its success. Students should demonstrate their acquired skills, knowledge, cognitive ability, intellectual ability, Meta competency, key competency, action competency, practical competency. Institution must develop effective self-accrediting mechanism to measure the achievement of the student

and record their performance. They also have to take help from external professional bodies to assess overall performance of the institution.

A Strong Track Record of Students Employability

Institute must maintain the records of their student's employment. It is a good way to assess the performance of student's and institutions. Well trained graduate has a potential to perform well in labour market and succeed in professional occupations. Institutions have to make multi-pronged strategy for the purpose and have to make education more attractive and have to prepare students for the world of work rather than achieving academic goals and simultaneously institutions have to create employment potential. To develop the employment opportunity institutions, have to maintain data bank of their passing out and passed out students. A good passed out student network help institutions for future employment opportunity.

Education for Employability

Educational institutions success largely depends upon its research-oriented teaching and learning and its student's employability skills. The use of higher education is to develop strength, expertise and skills to solve the problem of life. Institutions have to explore the potential of students and have to highlight the importance of job and of entrepreneurship. They have to explore the employable skills of students especially in commercial, managerial and technical area to match the industry requirement. They have to prepare students to get oriented towards setting up of the enterprise and generate employment and participate in nation economic growth. Institutes must boost spirit and confidence among students that "yes we can do it". Institute must motivate student that they develop the strength to change impossible into I, M Possible.

Fund Generation and Optimal Utilization of Academic Resources

Higher education institutions have to play multiple responsibilities. One side they have to generate financial resources and on other side they have to utilise its overall resources. It is found that global economic slowdown has influenced the government education policy to a large extent. Decline in public funding is expected and in reciprocation it will impact the education sector overall growth. Government and private educational institutions have to develop strategic and effective measures to mobilise resources for higher education. Government with consent of private higher education institutions have to develop strategic fee structure which should be related to the student's capacity to pay. Economically weak class must be provided subsidised education. Institutions have to utilise their academician's skills, ability, knowledge and expertise to strengthen its base. Apart of financial resources almost all institutional resources depend upon teachers. Quality of teachers converts average institution into world class institution. Students also have a role to play and institutions have to respect their participations. Satisfied

students are silent goodwill ambassador to the institutions and have a power to influence society and students. Thus, all academic and financial resources should be utilized to its potential. For the purpose institutions have to develop and adopt a well balance, effective and social policy.

Social and Private Sector Participation (SPP)

Government have to promote private sector to actively participate in education sector. It has to ensure SPP through appropriate policy. Nations higher education ministries have to play instrumental role in developing purposeful venture between universities, industries and national research institutions. Government have to play a parental role and have to encourage and facilitate private sector in research and higher education activities. Government have to set up excellent teachers training institute with the participation of industries. Success of industries depends upon student calibre, skills, ability, and knowledge, aptitude of learning and adoptive skills. To get such inputs they have to play special role and have to become active member in policy making. Higher education success and survival depends upon its institutional quality and nation's efficient school structure. To get input in institutions they have to play anchor role in strengthening the school base of the nation. Government may not limit private participation in higher education only, but they must be encouraged to be active in all levels of education system. From primary, higher secondary schools to higher education and research institutions.

Technological Up-gradation

Present regime is techno oriented and society is living in information age with highly developed integrated communication and information system. These technologies have flooded new and cost-effective approaches to educate the people. Through technology education has penetrated to the remotest area and levelled the field of opportunity for all. Higher education institutions have to keep on upgrading their strength by adopting new competitive technologies related to the educational sector. Through upgraded technology institutes can shape vision of academic success of all participants, they can create climate of hospitable to education, they can cultivate leadership in others, they can improve instruction and can manage people, data and can process to foster academic improvement. Institutions have to use modern technology as a weapon of acquiring knowledge and making them more effective and competitive in higher education. Through technology institutions can develop global awareness; creativity, collaborative problem solving and self-directed learning instinct among the students and other academic participants. It is a core and crucial requirement for the overall academic growth and development. Thus, higher education institutions can match the pace of competition only by adopting prevailing technologies of the time and through adopted modern technologies they will be able to establish innovative learning environment.

Equity and Academic Freedom

Academic freedom in higher education is essential. Higher education institutions are expected to be committed to the value of objective enquiry and pursuit of knowledge without any restraint and interference. Institutions must protect their dignity and equality of opportunity and their individuality. All students of the institutes must be treated equal and they should be promoted and motivated to avail educational opportunities and achieve and fulfil their potential dream. Institution must remove barriers that students face like, race, ethnicity, nationality, gender identity, disability, language ability, religion, socioeconomic status etc. Equality among the academic participant distinct institutions and make them excellent. Institutions can define their purpose and personality in many ways, but excellent institutions move on equity in diversity. Thus, higher education institutions have to maintain high degree of equity among students, teaching and non-teaching staff.

Global Commitment

To become excellent higher education institutions global perspective is paramount. Most of the higher education institutions across the world generally transmitting knowledge through traditional functions in which they use research activities, teaching, innovation, personality and human resource development along with education. But to become excellent higher education institution and to compete in international environment and to become part of international knowledge economy institutes have to promote global perspective in their mission and vision. Institutes have to benchmark their performance with comparable institutions within the nation and with institutions of other nations; they have to participate in national and international research and academic activities.

Recognising the Importance and Social Benefits of Higher Education

Higher education institution must recognise the importance and benefits of education. Education is necessarily required for social growth, peace and justice. It is core function of higher education institutions to foster the values of civilised society and to promote social mobility and social justice. To become excellent institution, they have to demonstrate high degree of commitment to social and cultural inclusion. Institutes have to expand their base with equity and have to excess the participation in higher education to all who have ability, desire and motivation to avail the benefits from the experience.

Stakeholder Satisfaction

Satisfying the stakeholders is one of the most important responsibilities of the institutions. It is not easy but a herculean task as it linked to the perceived performance of institutions which is evaluated through feedback from the stakeholder. Stakeholder includes wide range of different employees and other participants like industry, students, society, individuals, promoters who

are associated with the institution directly or indirectly and want to get, transfer and use knowledge and research outcomes. If institution wants to establish itself like an excellent institution of international repute, then it has to focus on the need and expectations of stakeholders. It has to equip its student according to the global standard so that they can fully meet the expectation of the employers and other interested parties.

Student Satisfaction

Among the stakeholders, students are one of the most important stakeholders and they have a right to receive quality education. Committed students and their outlook are assets not only to the institutions but also to the industry. Students overall performance, satisfaction and their learning experience is the best way to measure the quality education provided by the institution. Institutions have to conduct student satisfaction and exit surveys on the completion of their studies. Outcome of such survey should be taken into consideration in planning and policy making.

Research Oriented Academic Development

Research in education is necessary as it provide base for educational planning. It is one of the most important fields that should be core in higher education curriculum. Institutions get recognised by its research activities and by research-oriented teaching and learning. A good academic institution is always found of research activities, it involves vibrant academic community, academic staff, researchers and students. Quality and excellence of educational institutions is judged by its research involvement. The quantity and quality of research output measure the research activity of the institution. Through research teachers develop requisite knowledge and skills and become effective academic leader and perform better in classroom. Institutes have to promote research, it must appreciate teacher's efforts in research work and also encourage student to adopt research projects. Institute have to make a policy of incentive and must allot incentives to the research activities and achievements. It must increase the incentive time to time to encourage research participants.

Promotion of Effective Extracurricular Activities

Extracurricular activities are also known as co-curricular activities. These activities explore the potential of the students and lead to their total development. These activities groom the students and participating in such activities is directly related to improving their self-esteem, self-growth, developing confidence, leadership quality and involving them in social and political activities. It also contributes in better academic grades, higher academic aspirations, and self-control with decline incidences of delinquency. Good higher education institutions have to offer a significant range of extracurricular activities to their students throughout the year. It should be made part of their academic curricular. To offer such activities institutes also need faculties who have ability to conduct it. Thus, institute have to make a

sound policy for extracurricular activities and have to keep academic and industrial required activities as a core.

Establishing Effective Socio-Economic Culture

Higher education institutions have to develop, promote, and sustain socio-economic culture in the institution. It is essential as it is required by the local and regional community. To fulfil their missions through curriculum development, applied research, knowledge transfer and social welfare Institutions need these developments and all these developments require mental, physical and social infrastructure. Institutions have to play central role in the life of the communities and have to integrate, teaching, research, intellectual development, growth, innovation, technical skills, expertise, values and equity with society for their social and economic betterment. To become leader institutions, have to recognise number of goals in the light of present and future challenges and have to set futuristic targets with complementary policies.

Quality Audit

Internationalization of higher education requires quality, accountability and transparency. To meet the global academic requirement institutions, have to maintain academic quality and excellence. For the purpose of continuous improvement, it has to conduct internal and external academic and administrative audit time to time. Private higher education institutions have to fulfil the requirement of accreditation. They have to develop and maintain quality which is exceptional, exclusive, unique, distinctive, self-evident, perfect, standard, value addition, value for money, competent, efficient, effective, consistent and relevant. Through internal and external audit institutions can identify the deviation and can implement corrective measures to maintain academic and administrative quality.

Faculty Role in Higher Education

Education is an integrated and interdependence process. Its fundamental function is to transform future generation. It comprises of highly efficient and versatile faculties associated with functional hierarchy. All the faculties are employed on the basis of perceived needs of the institute and are generally regarded as a commodity. They play toughest role in the society. Without any autonomy they contribute in nation building. Through their knowledge, expertise and exploratory approach they convert dreams of society and mission and vision of the institutions into reality. They are architect of the future; they are processing machine which process future generation, they transform raw inputs into outputs of greater value, they create facilitating atmosphere for students and help them to shape their carrier and future, they play role of a guide, friend, father, brother, and they for their creativity, intelligence and everlasting contribution get valued, respected and honoured by the society and students. For their respect and versatility, faculties have to adopt quality management and have to keep on exploring their academic potential in order to impart quality education to the students with dignity.

Administrative Role

Institute administration has to play multiple roles strategically. They have to manage internal and external stakeholders, department, functions, faculty and students. As an administration they have to apply managerial leadership through participative management and have to play diversified range of roles. They have to play a role of mentor, facilitators, innovators, coordinator, integrator and promoters. People working in the institute have to follow the system and they cannot do better than the system allowed. Problem arises when good people join institution and it develop competitive environment which become problem for inefficient peoples. Administration has to create conducive working environment which promote team spirit, which minimise problems and provide solution, which facilitate academic participant to adopt continuous improvement, which build unity and integrity, which promote overall job satisfaction. Administration has to develop long term policy in which faculty and student partnership has to be developed through innovation and quality with low cost. Administration has to develop competitive, effective, efficient and transparent performance appraisal, recognition and reward systems. Administration must develop the séance of competition among the academic participants in natural competitive behaviour, but it must avoid putting one person or one group against another.

Institute must Minimise Accidental Teachers

Higher education institutions have to develop, maintain and protect team of highly research-oriented teaching faculties. They have to induct and associate teachers who have desire to do something new, who have ability to influence, inspire, motivate students, who have academic skills, analytical skills, efficiency and expertise. Institute must avoid and minimise accidental teachers who do not have any academic strength, who do not have any academic instinct, who do not have academic passion and orientation, who do not have any academic skills, who do not have subjective knowledge and expertise, who due to failure in carrier became teacher. Such teachers cannot become assets to the institutions. Such teachers mostly outsource their doctorate degree and prefer distance learning education to complete their qualification. Such teachers mostly have a desire to associate with power and to come close to the authority and they mostly act as an informer. They develop a group and try to hold maximum positions in the organization. They, to cover their academic and teaching inefficiency always busy in converting small thing into issues, they work untidily and plant evidences against good teachers, they are highly efficient in converting rope into snake, by developing unwanted issues they divert the attention of the management to other side, they are master in developing differences between management and good faculties to protect themselves, they through collective conspiracy provoke management to sack good faculties, they provoke students to file complain against good teachers so they can convert it into big issue and drive out

some advantage to satisfy their ego, they are highly egoist and work on conspiracy theory, they cannot be a solution but they will always problem or part of a problem, they just want sub stand academic environment in which they can survive, they oppose positive and competitive academic activities. Such teachers cannot groom students; they do teaching to complete the formality. They indulge in such activities because of fear that they cannot compete with good faculties and in result they have to face the consequences. Such accidental faculties constitute more than fifty percent of total teacher's strength in Indian sub-continent. Impact of such faculties is very drastic and can be seen at global level. According to the Clarivate Analytics published list comprising 4000 Global most Influential Researchers" India is far behind from other nations academic institutions. In top 1 percent highly, cited researchers (HCR) United States topped the list with 2,639 academicians, followed by UK, with 546 and China with 482 academicians. Indian academicians' number is found below to double digit and it was 4, later it is expected that Indian researchers' number will increase to 10 after including two cross field areas, and in that some of the researchers are not from the country leading institute. In comparison to Indian premier universities and institutes Harvard University 186 academicians are in the list. 15 years ago, India and china were at the same level, China is contributing 15 – 16 percent in science and India is contributing 3-4 percent only. This pathetic condition happens due to such inefficient academic faculties and needed to be arrested. Government and private institute must make extra efforts. Institutes for short term financial gain neglect long term loss and induct more such teachers. Such teachers covert institute into substandard and in result institute lose its image in society. To overcome such image institute, have to pay heavy price and it take more time to achieve the set target. Thus, for better future higher education institutes have to avoid and have to minimise such accidental teachers.

X. DISCUSSIONS & CONCLUSION

The main purpose of this paper was to explore the various dimension and develop a framework for bringing quality and achieving excellence in higher educational institution so as to meet the aspiration of future prospect. The higher educational institution in the country is an essential starting point for nation building. It is crucial to get in touch with what stake holders are looking for and what all are their aspirations. At the starting point, first raw material for the qualitative input are the students and their preparedness at the school as well as their basic abilities. (L.Acquero et al. 2009). Next one is the process element which include all the element necessary for transformation of raw material into finished product. These includes; faculties and required infrastructure. And at the later stage are the market support for the finished product. Higher educational

institute finished product are its students. Creating the infrastructural support like job opportunity, their education marketability, legal support, recognition at national as well as international level are some of the important activities that bring quality in education and helps in achieving excellence. India being a developing country always tries to develop and evolve new ways to connect to students. Many studies reported a significant positive relationship between academic achievement and academic performance. (Bryne and Flood 2008). The knowledge of motives and their convergence is important for policy maker related to expansion of higher education in the country. These motives act as change agents in transforming the students. It describes needs of effectiveness and new kinds of programmes and courses to deal with increasing student aspirations. New demands are described as having been placed on teachers, students and leadership, including an expanded role for student choices of and in higher education. Finally, this study highlights the convergence of motives of students for pursuing higher education and help in improved planning and more effective policymaking on the part of education in India. Further it is suggested that management should frame their policies that fulfils the students in acquisition of knowledge, skill and competencies, provide better future opportunities, enhancing self-efficiency, provide career prospect and helps students in gaining self-esteem. This will have significant effects on universities as well as on students in meeting their long-term goals and fulfilling aspirational values.

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